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An Assessment of the Effects of Drug Abuse on the Academic Performance of Students of Tertiary Institution in Nigeria: A Study of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina

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ABSTRACT

The problem of drug abuse among the students in Nigerian tertiary institutions has been receiving increasing attention in recent times. However, the causes of drug abuse among them have not really been identified to the extent that it can offer suggestions for adequate policy measures. and to a large extent differential effects of drugs on students' academic performance, health and social relationship, among others, are yet to be adequately interrogated. The main objective of study was to ascertain the effects of drug abuse on the academic performance of students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria with focus on students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina. The Social Learning Theory was employed as the theoretical framework for the research. Primary and secondary data were collected with the aid of structured questionnaire and interview guide using mixed method (Qualitative and Quantitative methods). The sample size for the study was 375 using Krejcie and Morgan's table formula of (1970.) The quantitative data was collected and analyzed using descriptive statistical model while the qualitative data collected through interview was narrated. The sample for the research were made up of males and females, across the University's faculties. The qualitative data was collected from NDLEA office Katsina, office of the Dean of Students Affairs UMYUK and office of the Chief Security Officer UMYUK. Findings of the study revealed that Codeine was the most commonly abused drug, Student Drop-out from School was the major effect of drug abuse, and male students are more prone to drugs abuse than female students in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University. Thus, the study recommended that, the Management of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University should continue organizing periodic seminars, workshops and presentations after orientation of fresh students, and establish a course related to effects of drug abuse on the academic performance of students even if it is one (1) credit unit and make it compulsory to all students.

Keywords: Drug, Drug Abuse, Academic Performance, Students

INTRODUCTION

Drug abuse constitute a serious threat to the survival and effective functioning of human societies, and lives are lost daily through addiction and activities of addicts. A significant number of deaths from accidents and violent crimes have been traced to the activities of persons under the influence of drugs. Excessive abuse of drug can cause physical or psychological dependence on individual. Also, it can bring conflict between the user and the society. It may lead to social problem and equally generate conflict within user and his social environment (Ejikeme 2011). World Health Organization (2015), drugs like alcohol, tobacco and cocaine are the root cause of road accident which have claimed lives and the high rate of sickness suffered by our societies today. The issue of drug abuse has become the main theme of discussion in our societies today.

Historically the world we live in reveals that drug abuse is a day to day increasing disaster because since early, consumption of drugs like psychoactive substances was strictly limited by elders who were to perform special social functions such as rituals, and other ceremonies. As the time went on there was an increased illegal use of drugs, hence the earliest record on prohibition of excessive consumption of alcohol was made clear in some areas. In 2000 BC the law was made in Egypt although the law was inefficiently working up to 1956 when some legal actions against drug abuse were at first introduced in USA. Furthermore, in the year 1950, so many Asian countries decided to initiate drug control policies and the death penalty for trafficking or possession of opium and its derivatives like heroin among other (Paulo, 2017). The report by (UNDCP, 2012) also revealed that 1.3 people or 30% of the world population are said to have used some tobacco and 230 million people which is an equivalence of 5% of the world population aged between 15 to 16 years consumed drugs illegally. The Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration provided a report that 9.8 million adults aged 18 and above in the United States had undergone a serious mental illness, among which a 1.7 million of them aged 18 to 25. Meanwhile 15.7 million of the adults aged 18 or above and 2.8 million youth aged 12 to 17) experienced a major depressive episode during their past years. Above all, in year 2014 there was an estimated 22.5 million Americans aged 12 and above who reported themselves to get alcohol or illicit drug use treatment, among them 11.8 million adults reported of asking for a mental health treatment and counseling as well in the past years (SAMHSA, 2014). Drug abuse affects school achievement of students in tertiary institutions, students who have smoked are more likely to have decreased attentiveness, cognitive, memory functions, difficult remembering information and verbal learning impairment, drop out of school, school achievement deterioration over time and engage in delinquent behavior which at the end affects their academics performance cited in Sa'adu, (2012).

In year 2013 it was reported that East Africa was a major target for traffickers wanted to enter African markets and this would be easier due to its unprotected coastline, major seaports and airports and porous land borders that provided many entries and exit points. Heroin was brought to East Africa directly from Afghanistan, Pakistan and Burma through Thailand and much of it found its way to South Africa, but there was also a reverse movement of drugs from South Africa to Tanzania and Kenya (UNODC, 2013). A UNODC map showed that heroin and cocaine also filtered across the borders of Tanzania into Mozambique, Malawi and Zambia. Some of it was shifted onwards to the United States and Western Europe. Abuse of drugs by students has been shown to affect academic performance in western African countries. In addition to this, drug abuse also affects students' academic performance negatively and destroys their physical, social and psychological stability, leading to thuggery, stealing/armed robbery, rape and other social vices seem to be very predominant among drug users as has been shown by various reports and studies. Students involved in abuse of drugs and substances also tend to experience financial difficulties as the little money that could be used for other important things are channeled towards purchase of more and more drugs (Tulu & Keski, 2015).

In Nigeria, the National African seminar on held problems of drug in Lagos, Nigeria declared that "Drug abuse are broadly prevalent in African countries have continue to increase. These problems affect the individual, the family and the society in general. Substance abuse, which was originally conceived as the

problem of a selected few is today becoming a problem of a sizeable proportion of the world population. The predicament is so grave that it has extended beyond the usual characteristic of abusers being male, adult, and urban-based to now include females, youngsters and those who live mostly in the northern part of Nigeria. Its economic effect is so upsetting that it is estimated that the annual retail cost of psychotropic drug by prescription is over two billion naira while the alcoholic company which produces over five billion gallons of alcoholic beverages annually generate more than four billion naira from sales to a consumer population of about 30-35 million people (Folawiyo, 2008 cited in Adewale, 2012). Drug and substance abuse among secondary school students has been linked to, intolerance, violence, insecurity, and antisocial behavior in schools that pose difficulties in management of schools. It has also been linked to students' poor academic performance; defiance to school rules and regulations and poor student academic performance in secondary schools in the Nigerian states such as Ekiti and Ondo States (Nwakwo, Nwoke 2010). Nigeria is one of the leading countries with big numbers of users of cannabis and other drugs; with about 5 to 10% using alcohol, cannabis, and other drugs. In 2008, 2000 users of cannabis in Katsina State were prosecuted and imprisoned Bashar I. et al. (2019). As a consequence of the prevalence of drug abuse in society the schools are longer places where the imparting of morals is a challenge. The students abuse drugs like tobacco, alcohol, tramadol, cough syrup, and other caffeinated substances such as Nescafe to reduce pain, anxiety and tension. Some of the reasons for their use are; parental background, peer group influence, isolation and loneliness. Other reasons are elevation of mood, wakefulness, increased confidence and feeling of euphoria (Linhadt ;2001 as cited in Bashar I., Fauziya I., B., Ibrahim L. A., Abubakar J. J. (2019).

Available report indicates that Nigeria is also one of the highest consumers of cannabis and amphetamine in Africa (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2011). Thus, the International Council for Alcohol and Addiction (1988) observes that the problem of drug abuse has for a considerable time increasingly escalated in Nigeria. It is an observable fact which is being emphasized by the present economic dilemma which the nation has found itself with its attendant social discontent. Until recently, drug abuse was not very prevalent in Nigeria, because these drugs are not produced in Nigeria and are therefore not readily available (cited in Yahaya, 2013). Okafor (2020), states that drug abuse among Nigerian youths has been a scourge to the overall sustainable development of the nation. Substance abuse is a serious issue; a global and international issue particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. Drug abuse is also a major public health, social and individual problem and is seen as an aggravating factor for economic crises, hence led to poverty in Nigeria. While youths are supposed to be the major agent of change and development, some of them have been destroyed by drug abuse. Educational stakeholders like parents, teachers and the society at large are worried over the prevalence of drug abuse and its causes and consequences on the undergraduates of the University of Ilorin in Kwara state. Equally, Akanbi, Anyio, Muhammad and Ajiboye (2014). In Nigeria, also it has been consistently reported that drug abuse is a widespread social practice among tertiary school students. Many factors have been found to influence tertiary school students to indulge in drug abuse. These factors include family factors (e.g., lack of parental care, low-income family background, marital breakdown), school factors (e.g., educational stress, poor teacher-student relationships, poor academic performance, absence from lecture), economic factors (e.g., unemployment, poor feeding) psychological factors (e.g., frustration, and emotional stress), and others. Unfortunately, drug abuse is becoming a monstrous problem in Nigerian society (Abubakar G.I., Shahu H. and Sani Y., 2022).

Abuse of drugs by students has been linked to poor academic performance because a study by Njeru and Ngesu (2014) indicated that 52% of students believed that drug abuse causes poor performance as 30% agreed that their colleagues who abused drugs develop aggressive behaviour. The findings of different other studies have shown that declining grades, absenteeism from class/other activities, and increased potential for dropping out of school or university are problems associated with adolescent alcohol and drug abuse (Didenko & Pankratz, 2007). Additionally, low level of commitment to education and higher absence rates appear to be related to alcohol and drug use among adolescents in the universities and

colleges. According to Attah, Baba and Audu (2016), students who abused drugs spend much money on the purchase of these drugs at the detriment of purchasing their academic books. A study by Muhammad *et al.* (2012) reported that 70 (48.5%) out of 200 respondents agreed to have missed classes as a result of drug use. All these in turn lead to poor academic performance by the students. According to Sternberg (2003), drug abuse affects learners' academic performance negatively. Because drugs affect the brains as a result there is a major decline in brain functionality. This means they will begin to take longer to process information and come out with answers. Some pupils will begin to concentrate more on drugs than school. Some become so addicted such that they end up missing lessons or eventually dropping out of school looking for drugs and if lessons are missed out, performance dwindles.

In Katsina State, Amina, (2018) reported that, Drug Abuse is on increased in Katsina State and indeed Nigeria as a whole. She also stated that, this because the present strategies of fighting drugs abuse based on rational choice theory, which supports the view that, the way to control human behavior is through more severe punishment, through the state agencies such as police, court and prison. Sa'adu (2015) stated that, drug abuse had become a challenging problem to the lives and success of the youth as it can be evidently not only as a source of sorrow to the parents, guardians and relatives but it is also a big challenge to the nation wholly. Yusuf, at el (2021), also reported that, Drug and substance abuse among the undergraduate university students in Katsina State is common, and it cuts across both male and female students. Most abused drugs are cough syrups, codeine (in all forms), and sleeping pills (tranquilizers), while of the substance type, tobacco, cannabis, coffee, and inhalants are the most commonly abused. However, there was no record regarding female abusing inhalants. A significant number of the respondents have information regarding the consequences of drug and substance abuse. Moreover, the university environment has no influence on the abusers regarding their indulgence into the menace. Finally, the abuse practice has serious negative impacts on the students' zeal to attend lectures and their academic performance. Therefore, stakeholders and members of the public should act urgently in order to reduce the growing rate of drug abuse especially among the youth who will be our tomorrow' leaders.

Statement of the Research Problem

According to Yusuf, Garba, Zayyanu, & Umar (2021) drug and substance abuse among the undergraduate university students in Katsina State is common, and it cuts across both male and female students. Concerted efforts towards parental support and supervisions, social intervention programs, and campus-based prevention and supported programs against drug and substance abuse should be encouraged. Despite the focus, concentration, attention and intervention strategies by the religious organizations, Government, non-governmental organizations, civil societies, and many other organizations or stakeholders to reduce the problem of drug abuse among the students of higher institutions, still the number of drug abusers keep increasing and everyday this leads to many social problems in our tertiary institutions in Katsina and in Nigeria at large such as violence, sexual abuse, low performance, conflict among the students and lecturers, which always lead to negative consequences to our educational development because the problems has spread its tentacles to all nooks and crannies in the Nigerian society. This has therefore prompted this study.

Research Question

To what extent drug abuse affects the academic performance of students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina?

Research Objective

The objective of this study is to assess the effects of drug abuse on the academic performance of students of tertiary institutions in Nigeria with reference to Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Research Hypothesis

There is no significance relationship between drug abuse and academic performance of students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Operationalization of Concepts

i. Drug Abuse: In this research work drug abuse is seen to mean a process of taking drugs without proper consultation of medical professional or practitioners on the guideline of taking it. Drug abuse is a situation whereby an individual takes it for purposes other than medical reasons.

ii. Academic Performance

Academic Performance can be seen to mean gaining knowledge; acquiring skills and competencies; securing high grades and similar academic achievements; securing a progressive career; and intention and persistence towards education.

Literature Review

Drug Abuse

Medline's medical encyclopedia defines drug abuse as the use of illicit drugs or the abuse of prescription or over-the-counter drugs for purposes other than those for which they are indicated or in a manner or in quantities other than directed (Buddy, 2011 cited in Yahaya, 2013).

In 1932, the American Psychiatric Association drug abuse refers to apply to the illegal, nonmedical use of a limited number of substances, most of them drugs, which have properties of altering the mental state in ways that are considered by social norms and defined by statute to be inappropriate, undesirable, harmful, threatening, or, at minimum, culture-alien. Glasscote, Sussex, Jaffe, Ball, & Brill, 1932, (cited in Yahaya, 2013).

According to Lewinsohn Rohde, and Brown (1999), drug abuse is a widespread and potentially hazardous activity, increasing risks for dependence and abuse and other adverse physical and psychosocial outcomes. Drugs abuse is a problem that countries throughout the world have had to contend with for centuries. Globally, it is estimated that in 2012, some 243 million people of the world population aged 15-64 had used an illicit drug, mainly a substance belonging to the cannabis, opiates, cocaine or amphetamine-type stimulant (ATS) groups, at least once in the previous year (World Drug 2014 cited in Deborah, 2017).

According to Edwe and Joshua, (2017) stated that, drug is said to be abused when its use is not pharmacological or physically necessary it can also be used to describe a situation whereby the dosage of a given drug is exceeded by the user.

For the purpose of this research work, drug abuse is seen to mean a process of taking drugs without proper consultation of medical profession of practitioners on the guidelines of taking it. Drug abuse is a situation whereby an individual takes it for purposes other than medical reasons.

Drug abuse is also seen as a process of violating the rules and regulations regulating and controlling the drugs usage by any individual.

Academic Performance

Kumar, et al (2021). Stated that, Academic Performance can be defined in terms of gaining knowledge; acquiring skills and competencies; securing high grades and similar academic achievements; securing a progressive career; and intention and persistence towards education. Academic Performance is highest for academic achievement followed by knowledge gained as well as skills and abilities acquired York et al., 2015 (cited in Kumar, at al 2021).

The academic performance of students is the key feature (Rono, Onderi & Owino, 2014) and one of the important goals (Narad and Abdullah, 2016) of education, which can be defined as the knowledge gained by the student which is assessed by marks by a teacher and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to be achieved over a specific period of time (cited in Kumar, at al 2021). The attainment of academic excellence of students through making them portray better academic performance is the foremost motive of academic institutions (Adeyemo, 2001). Further, academic performance is something immensely significant for anyone who has a concern with education Osiki, 2001 (cited in Kumar, at al 2021).

According to Díaz-Morales and Escribano (2015), academic performance is to be understood as the result of a combination of psychological, social, and economic factors, which further lead to the proper multifaceted growth of students (cited in Kumar, et al 2021).

Kumar, et al (2021) reported that, academic performance can be understood as the nucleus, around which a whole lot of significant components of education system revolve, which is why the academic performance of students, specifically belonging to Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), has been the area of interest among researchers, parents, policy framers and planners. Since a sound academic performance is considered as a pre-requisite for securing good jobs, a better career and subsequently a quality life, significance of the students' academic performance is immense. Although it may seem to be a simple outcome of education, but the impact of academic performance of students in any nation is multi-faceted. According to Edwe and Joshua, (2017) stated that, Academic Performance: Is the outcome of education - the extent to which a student, teacher or Institution has achieved their educational goals.

For the purpose of this research work, academic performance refers to the process by which the students put their best in achieving or obtaining the academic qualification through hard work. Academic performance also is a process whereby a student of institutions has graduated with best result.

Review of Empirical Studies

Many years passed, the issue of drug abuse and other illicit substances among youth, adolescence and adults it is said to be a burning issue in the history of mankind. There are many researchers and authors who have reported various negative impacts among students who involved in drug abuse like HIV/AIDS, school absenteeism, destructive, poor academic performance and other deviant behaviors (Davis, 2001 as cited in Paulo, 2017).

Ondieki and Mokua (2012) found that peer influence played a major role in learners' use of drugs with 45% of alcohol users and 33% of the smokers having copied the habit from their friends. Shibalika (2021) in his study 'the causes and effects of drug abuse among primary school learners in Shibuyunji district of Zambia' states that the causes of drug abuse in Shibuyunji district were peer pressure, lack of recreational activities, curiosity and amusement, lack of parental supervision, prevalence of drugs in the locality and poverty, and that the effects of drug abuse were deviant behavior, predisposing crime, drug addiction, rebellious behavior towards authority, lower academic performance and expulsion or suspension from school. He further recommends the need to strengthen guidance and counseling in schools, and to enhance communication between administration and learners about the need for drug-free school environments (cited in Mercy, 2022).

Yusuf, et al (2021) reported that, In Nigeria, the prevalence of drug abuse accounts for about 14.4% or 14.3 million people aged between 15 and 64 years, which is comparatively high in comparison to the global annual prevalence of 5.6%. This has been the most important factor contributing to many social vices, mostly among the youth with the highest level of any past drug use among those aged 25-59 years. Students play an important role in the social and economic development programs and management of community; paying attention to their issues in different dimensions, particularly their mental aspect should not be neglected. Of the estimated 14.4% prevalence of people who use drug, our study center, Katsina, Nigeria, accounts for an estimated prevalence of 12% of most drug types is high among young people within the age range of 25 and 39 years. It is one of the reasons why we are undertaking this study to investigate the prevalence of drug abuse amongst students which are predominantly youths.

According to (UNDCP, 2002 as cited in Paulo, 2017) reported that, marijuana consumption was said to be widely spread in Africa. It was said that beyond 25 million of consumers constituted 5.8% of the adult population whereby the world average was 3.4% of the adult population. In African continent it was said that 61% of people who got treated for drug abuse were often displayed with the serious psychological disorders and mostly were cannabis users and 2/3 of them were youth.

According to (Agbonghalel and Okaka, 2014) who investigated the effects of drug abuse on academic performance on technology education students in Nigerian public universities found that 82.79% of the

population who participated in study agreed that hard drugs had some effects on academic performance of technology education students in Nigerian public universities who involved in drug abuse. According to (Otieno, 2012) who conducted a study on environmental and demographic factors influencing drug and substance abuse among secondary school students in Kisumu town east in Kenya, indicated some statistical information from Kisumu District Hospital to have an increase in mental and behavioral disorders due multiple drug consumption and the use of other psychoactive substances (KDH Office, 2012). In 2010, those between the age of 15-24 years who were admitted in the very hospital with mental and behavioral disorders due to drug abuse were about three, among them one patient died from psychotic disorders. Meanwhile in year 2011, there were psychiatric cases related to multiple drug use and other psychoactive substances within secondary school age (15-24) years which increased to ten so this percentage increase was almost 33%. As the results deaths that arose from drug and other substances abuse continued to increase one year after another in Kisumu town (KDH, 2012).

Tuwei, 2014, in his study on influence of drug abuse on students' academic performance in public universities showed that alcohol abuse influences on academic performance such as heavy drinking which has got a negative effect. Marijuana abuse was said also to directly impair academic abilities that limit academic performance and the minority of students who were daily marijuana dealt with highly segregated ways of behavior were noted to involve in criminal behaviors such as breaking laws or when individuals involved in criminal acted to fund their drug abusers (Tuwei, 2014).

Causes of drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions

Kiiru (2004) supports the view that peer pressure influences the students to abuse drug under the false impression that some drugs stimulate appetite for food, increase strength and give wisdom as well as courage to face life. Jorisc at el (2012) looks at parental neglect as the cause of drug abuse among students. His view was that parents who failed to guide and protect their children, their children are most likely to abuse drugs, unlike parent's children whose parents are protective, supportive, and show love and affection to their children. Bandura (1997) acknowledges in his social learning theory that one of the causes of drug abuse among students is observation and modeling. This theory supports the view that students' abuse drugs upon observing and modeling. When students see their role models from movie stars to musicians or television personalities abusing drugs, they are most likely to abuse drugs, meanwhile ignoring the dangers of drug abuse. Kassandra (2009) also observes poor grades as one of the major causes of drug abuse among students. Kassandra states that the low grades create negative feelings among students, and so to ease the pain and low morale, students resort to drug abuse as a remedy to their failures in effort to gain self-confidence. Kirru (2004) 'recognizes financial background as one of the causes of drug abuse among students. He states that some students from wealthy families abuse drugs because they can afford them, unlike their counterparts from poor families who may resort to cheap drugs like alcohol to temporarily forgot their problems, and calm down their frustrations arising from lack of tuition and other basic needs.

Adelekan (2005) states that the social media is a universal factor influencing drug abuse among students in developed and developing countries. This is most common in urban centers where young people are more exposed to television, internet access, billboard adverts, and radio among other forms of media which are bombarded with adverts promoting drugs like tobacco and alcohol. Bazuidenhout, (2004) states that parents abusing drugs are most likely to experience children who abuse drug, he goes on to say that parents abusing drugs experience a higher rate of parental and family problems than to students whose parents do not abuse drugs. This may therefore bring about parental attachment to their children, hence chances of a student abusing drug, given the fact that their parents are not available to provide support and counsel. Johnston (2000), also states that social pressures also reinforce drug abuse among students as it is seen as a sign of adult behavior. As such, students who grow older with age and become economically independent are most likely to abuse drugs. In addition, students may abuse drugs for reasons like relaxation, relieving stress, showing independence, get rid of boredom, being included in a social group, curiosity among others.

According to Rimfat (1999); it is understood that students take drugs for the following reasons;

i. Parental Imitation; some adolescent and students take drugs like alcohol, hem, and dine family syrup etc. because their parents, elders, brothers, cousins, uncles, friends and lecturers or teachers are taking them. In the light of this, Gangara (1997) stated that “adolescents used drugs in imitation of their parents for the excitement of doing the forbidden”

ii. Availability of Drugs; in the light of this Idegbe (2002), cited that if drugs are available in the community there will be easy access to them.

For example, the former, Executive Governor of Kano State, Dr. Rabi’u Musa Kwankwaso during his tenure, took a giant stride in the fight against drugs abuse by reduced considerably the presence of drug hawkers and drug dealers in the metropolitan of Kano City.

iii. Seek for Popularity; academically weak students can take to excessive drinking and the use of drugs in-order to attract attention and become famous among colleagues and the school authority, just to show their dissatisfaction.

iv. Secret Cult; drug abuse is one of the causes of Secret Cult in Nigerian higher institutions and in the society at large. Smah (1997), asserted that the relationship between drug abuse and violence is undeniable. For instance:

The abuse of drugs by different social categories especially the youth, leads to running of the central nervous system, weakening of the power of judgment, anxiety, sleeplessness, irritability, irresponsible behavior etc.

The above points to the fact that students take drugs in order to cause trouble, violence and engage in crimes, a reflection of this is clearly demonstrable in the rampant cases of cultism in many campuses of higher institutions such as Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges of Education.

v. Bright and Intelligent; some students take drugs to feel bright and intelligent and pass exams with flying colors. (Rimfat 1999) cited that students do these by engaging in the use of Kola-nut, Caffeine, Alcohol and Hem. Experience has shown that quite a number of them end-up performing below expectation; others end-up not even writing their exams.

Factors influencing substance abuse

Research has identified the following factors affecting substance abuse as highlighted by Sa’adu, (2012).

i. Role of Media

Role of media is the major factor affecting substance abuse control program in Nigeria. There is no restriction on alcohol advertising in Nigeria. In the advertisements of cigarettes and alcohol, people who smoke and drink are portrayed as sexy, manly and sophisticated. Advertising alcohol in Africa focuses on the youth, strength and nutritional values. This has a facilitating role for adolescents who are still trying to find their identity. According to Jokinen, Pitkainen and Hirvonen (2004) a popular advertisement in Cote D’Ivoire showed a young person on a motorbike who was very exhausted but was revived after drinking a bottle of beer. Also, even though Indian hemp is not advertised on media...? All these make impressions on the developing adolescents mind. (Cambor, Millman, 2009).

ii. Family Influence

An adolescent raised in a family whose member such as a parent or sibling abuses drugs is more likely to do the same. Similarly, parental attitudes or the youths’ perceived parental attitudes have a strong influence on the adolescents’ perceived decision making. In both cases, alcohol is introduced by close respected family members’ grandfather and elder brother respectively.

iii. Social Factors

Palm wine is an important alcoholic beverage in West Africa obtained from the juices of the oil palm and raffia palm plants. Palm wine is the most common traditional beverage used widely especially in the

southern part of Nigeria at wedding and funeral ceremonies. Alcohol is readily available especially in the southern region of Nigeria in shops, bars and hotels. This is sold to underage children although licenses granted for its sale require that only adults would buy, but rules are not obeyed. The situation is however different in some of the Northern states where religious (Islamic) laws have been enacted to ban the sale of alcohol.

iv. Psychological Dynamics

The need to conform and impress their peers was quite obvious in adolescents. As the adolescents' body matures, several changes occur. Parental influence in issue of lifestyle reduces the influence of peers increase and of the need to conform to their peer group becomes more dominant. A child may take up smoking or drinking alcohol so that they are drawn closer to group where this is the norm. In a study of drug use among junior high school children in Japan, peer pressure measured by been tempted to use demonstrated the highest risk factor with adjusted odd ration of 9.53, which was followed by problems.

Impact of drugs abuse on academic performance of students

Research has identified the following impact of drugs abuse on academic performance of students as highlighted in Sa'adu, (2012).

i. Smoking and academic performance of students

Smoking is strongly correlated with academic performance. Students who earn better grades are less likely to smoke. The Washington State Healthy Youth Survey conducted by the Department of Health, OSPI Department of Social and Health Services and Office of Community Development survey nearly 140,00 students in 752 schools statewide in October of 2002. The survey found that among the 8th grade student who receives most of D and F grades.23.7% were smokers. Among the C students 13.9 were smokers, 8.2% of students reporting mostly B were smokers and grade A 3.9% were smokers.

Moreover smoking affects school achievement of children, children who have smoked are more likely to decrease attentiveness, cognitive, and memory functions, have difficult remembering information and verbal learning impairment, (Yale 2005, Garrett, Dube, Trosclair, Caraballo and Pechacek, 2011) drop out of school (Koivusilta, Rimpel and Vikat, 2003, Vartiaine and Haukkala, 2004), have school achievement detoration over time (Brook, Balka, Rosen, Brook and Adams 2005), and engage delinquent behavior (Bachman, O' Malley, Johnston, Freedman Doan and Messersmith, 2008; Bryant and Zimmerman, 2002, Tucker, Ellickson, and Klein, 2003; Van den Bree, Whitmer and Pickworth, 2004; UNICEF, 2007). Smoking among Jodanian school students rose rome 13% in 2004 to 20% in 2007 (Nsour, Mahfoud, Kanaan and Balbeissi, 2008) cited in Sa'adu, (2012).

ii. Alcoholism and academic performance of students

Clinical studies have found that heavy drinking impairs brain functioning. Nordby et al (1999) reviewed evidence that alcohol intoxication reduces recall for a period extending beyond the period of inebriation. Both Deas et al (2000) and DeBellis et at (2000) linked four alcohol disorders to reduction in the brain functioning among adolescence. Wuethrich (2001) showed evidence from studies of magnetic resonance imaging that sustained alcohol abuse destroys brain matter. These findings suggest that heavy drinking among adolescence that leads to drunkenness will have adverse cognitive effect that deleteriously impact school performance cited in Sa'adu, (2012).

iii. Chewing and academic performance of students

The habit of chewing Mira (Catha Edulis) is highly prevalent in east Africa and Southwestern Arabian Peninsula (Gegissa 2010). The fresh leaves and twigs of the Mira shrub have a stimulating amphetamine like and euphoric effect when chewed. Mira consumption has substantially increased in decades. This is reflected in the recent issue of the World Drug Report (2001) which reported an increase of Mira chewing in five countries.

The habit of chewing Mira is spreading at an alarming rate among the younger generation, especially in high schools and higher institutions, where academic activity is intense. Students in secondary schools, colleges and university usually use Mira, claiming that it improves their academic performance although

studies have shown significant difference between the mean Cumulative Grade Points Average (CGPA) of Mira users and those who do not chew Mira in favor of the later. This indicated that Mira chewing may not improve academic performance. Mira is usually chewed at special social gatherings, but is also used frequently during work by laborers, craftsmen, farmers, farmer and students to help them keep alert and reduce physical fatigue. Because of its stimulating effect it has been traditionally used as a medicine by students preparing for examinations (Sheikh et al 2014).

Theoretical Framework

The Social Learning Theory

Drug abuse among the students of tertiary institutions can be traced back to the theory known as the Social learning theory propounded by Bandura, (1977). This theory suggests that all behaviors whether delinquent, deviant or good, are learnt through observation, and imitation. From the theory we deduce that most of the students learnt the use and abuse of drugs from watching others doing it. The case becomes serious if the colleagues, brothers, sisters or fathers uses them while the children are watching. In other words, if daddy is doing it then it's the right thing to do. The theory also suggests that young people also learn through imitating their peers. They do this so as to blend in with their peers. This was normally the most important thing to a young child at a younger stage of growth. They want to be noticed, to do what was being done by others. So, if others are doing drugs and say they "feel cool", "out of this world", "invincible", then they feel they should try it also. So basically, they learn to do drugs because of peers who pressure them through telling them how much fun it was to try and they become curious to try it.

Applicability:

The theory is applicable to this research because the environment which the researcher conducted the research within the environment that comprised thousands of students from different angles (states) in Nigeria with difference cultural background, so there is propensity for students to learn and imitate drug abuse through socialization with their colleagues in the learning environment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the convergent mixed method design because it is a design that simultaneously collect both quantitative and qualitative data, merge the data, and use the results to understand a research problem.

Sources of Data

In this study, both primary and secondary data and their sources were employed. The primary data were generated from staff and students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina and Nigeria Drugs Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) staff Katsina State Office. While the secondary data were generated from security department and Students Affairs offices of UMYUK and other sources such as library and internet sources.

Population of the study

The population of this study consisted staff and students (13,277) of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, and Nigerian Drugs Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) staff Katsina State Office.

Sample Size

Sampling size refers to the process of selecting a given number of people from a defined population to be representative of the total population.

The sample size for this study is (375) out of the total population of (13,277) undergraduate students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, this was determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) Table formula.

Sampling Technique

In this study, the probability sampling technique was used in order to give equal chance to the entire population. Cluster sampling was also employed so as to get a representation of the entire population. Faculties within the Umaru Musa Yar'adua University were considered as clusters to generate data.

Instruments/Method of Data Collections

For the purpose of this study, questionnaire and interview were employed as the instruments of data collection.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The data collected were presented in tabular form, and analyzed using the descriptive statistical model. Chi-square was used to test the hypothesis because it is one of the non-parametric test statistics that is used to test the significant relation between variables.

Decision Rule

- i. Accept Null Hypothesis (Ho) if calculated value is less (<) than the critical value (table value) and reject Alternative Hypothesis (H1)
 - ii. Accept Alternative Hypothesis (H1) if calculated value is greater (>) than critical value (table value) and reject the Null Hypothesis (Ho).
- All the arrays of the null hypotheses (Ho) for the study will be tested using the same method formula.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Three hundred and seventy-five (375) copies of the questionnaires were distributed to the respondents that were involved in the study, but three hundred and sixty-six 366 (97.6%) of them were returned and found useful for the analysis while nine (9) 2.4% were unreturned

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	256	69.9
Female	110	30.1
Total	366	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2023

Table 1 shows that 256 representing (69.9%) of the respondents that participated in to this research were males while 110 representing (30.1%) were females. This shows that most of the respondents were males because males always constituted the major percentage of the population of students in tertiary institutions.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 20 yrs	89	24.3
20 - 30 yrs	240	65.6
31 - 35 yrs	28	7.7
36 - 40 yrs	9	2.5
50 years and above	0	0.0
Total	366	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2023

Table 2 displays the distribution of the respondents by age where 89 representing (24.3%) of the respondents were below the age of 20 years. However, 240 representing (65.6%) of the respondents were at the age interval of 20-30 years, 28 representing (7.7%) of the respondents were at the age interval of 31-35 while 9 representing (2.5%) of the respondents aged 36-40 years. This shows that, majority of the respondents representing (65.6%) were at the aged of between 20 to 30 years.

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents by Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	289	79.0
Married	72	19.7
Widow	3	.8
Divorcee	2	.5
Total	366	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2023

Table 3 shows that 289 representing (79%) of the respondents were single, 72 representing (19.7%) of the respondents were married, 3 representing (0.8%) of the respondents were widows while 2 (0.5%) were divorced. This shows that majority of the respondents were single.

Table 4 Distribution of Respondents by Faculty

Faculty	Frequency	Percentage
Faculty of Social and Management Sciences	69	18.9
Faculty of Humanities	43	11.7
Faculty of Education	96	26.2
Faculty of Natural and Applied Sciences	104	28.4
Faculty of Law	19	5.2
Faculty of Medicine	17	4.6
Faculty of Agriculture	18	4.9
Total	366	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2023

Table 4 shows that 69 of the respondents representing (18.9%) comes from the faculty of social and management sciences, 43 of the respondents representing (11.7%) comes from the faculty of humanities. However, 96 of the respondents representing (26.2%) comes from the faculty of education, 104 of the respondents representing (28.4%) comes from the faculty of natural and applied sciences. Moreover, 19 of the respondents representing (5.2%) comes from the faculty of law, 17 of the respondents representing (4.6%) comes from the faculty of medicine while 18 of the respondents representing (4.9%) comes from the faculty of agriculture. This shows that, majority of the respondents were from the Faculty of Natural and Applied Sciences.

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents by Level of Education

Level of education	Frequency	Percentage
100 Level	65	17.8
200 Level	101	27.6
300 Level	66	18.0
400 Level	116	31.7
500 Level	6	1.6
Spillover	12	3.3
Total	366	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2023

Table 5 shows the distribution of respondents by level of education where 65 (17.8%) were 100 level students, 101 (27.6%) were 200 level students, 66 (18.0%) were 300 level students, 116 (31.7%) were at 400 level, 6 (1.6%) were at 500 level while 12 (3.3%) were spillover students. This shows that most of the respondents were in the four hundred (400L) during this research.

Table 6: Distribution of Respondents by Family Background

Family background	Frequency	Percentage
Monogamy	205	56.5
Polygamy	161	44.5
Total	366	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2023

The distribution of respondents by family background in table 6 shows that majority of the students 205 representing (56.5%) comes from monogamy family, 161 of the respondents representing (44.5%) comes from polygamy family while 20 (5.5%) comes from divorcee family background.

Table 7: Most abused drugs among UMYUK Students

Drugs	Frequency	Percentage
Cocaine	29	7.9
Marijuana	28	7.7
Alcohol	13	3.6
Inhalants	6	1.6
Codeine	253	69.1
Cannabis	36	9.8
Others	1	.3
Total	366	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2023

Table 7 shows that 29 of the respondents representing (7.9%) said Cocaine was among the drugs students were taken, 28 of the respondents representing (7.7%) said Marijuana was among the drugs students were taken, 13 of the respondents representing (3.6%) said Alcohol was among the drug students were mostly taken, 6 of the respondents representing (1.6%) said Inhalants were among the drugs students were taken, 253 of the respondents representing (69.1%) said Codeine was among the drugs students were mostly taken, 36 of the respondents representing (9.8%) Cannabis was among the drug students were taken, while 1 representing (0.3%) were among others as shown in figure 1. This shows that Codeine representing (69.1%) was the most commonly drugs abused by the students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Table 8: Effect of drug Abuse on academic performance of students of UMYUK

Effect	Frequency	Percentage
Student Drop-Out	85	23.2
Irregular in Class Attendance	82	22.4
Brain Damage	48	13.1
Examination Malpractice	41	11.2
Suspension and Expulsion from School	39	10.7
Memory Loss	29	7.9
Sleeping Problem	22	6.0
Aggression	6	1.6
Bullying	2	.5
Lack of Seriousness in Assignments	12	3.3
Total	366	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2023

Table 8 contains the results of respondents regarding the effect of drug abuse on academic performance of UMYUK students. Among the respondents, 85 (23.2%) said students drop-out was among the major effect, 82 (22.4%) said irregular in class attendance was among the effects, 48 (13.1%) of them said brain damage, 41(11.2%) said examination malpractice was among the effects. However, 39 (10.7%) of the respondents said suspension and expulsion from school was among the major effects of drug abuse 29 (7.9%) said memory loss affects the students involved in drug abuse. Other effect of student's drug abuse includes sleeping problem 22(6.0%), aggression 6(1.6%), bullying 2 (0.5%) and lack of seriousness in assignments with 12 respondents representing 3.3%. this show that Students Drop-out is the most effect of drug abuse on the academic performance of UMYUK students as shown in figure 2.

Table 9: Gender Status that abuse Drugs more in UMYUK

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	309	84.4
Female	57	15.6
Total	366	100.0

Sources: Primary Data 2023

From table 9, the responses on gender status that abuse drugs more shows that 309 students representing 84.4% said it is males that mostly abused drugs in UMYUK while 57 students representing 15.6% said it is females that mostly abused drugs in UMYUK. This indicates that, it is males that were mostly abusing drugs in UMYUK.

Table 10: Factor that leads students to drug abuse in UMYUK

Factor	Frequency	Percentage
Peer group	203	55.5
Parental imitation	30	8.2
Availability of drugs	26	7.1
Seeking popularity	14	3.8
Secret cult	5	1.4
Perceived performance enhancer	6	1.6
Depression	24	6.6
Unemployment/Inactivity/Idleness	17	4.6
Poor academic performance	16	4.4
Societal failure	11	3.0
Health challenges	14	3.8
Total	366	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2023

Table 10 revealed the student's responses on the factor that leads students to drug abuse in UMYUK. The result shows that 203 students representing (55.5%) said that, peer group were among the factors, 30 students representing (8.2%) said parental imitation, 26 students representing (7.1%) said availability of drugs leads to students to drug abuse in UMYUK.

However, 14 students representing (3.8%) said some students were abusing drugs for seeking popularity, 5 students representing (1.4%) said some students were abusing drugs for secret cult perceived, 6 students representing (1.6%) said students usually abuse drugs as their performance enhancer.

Moreover, 24 respondents representing (6.6%) believed that UMYUK students abused drugs to reduce depression, 17 students representing (4.6%) of the respondents said students were taking drugs as a result of unemployment/inactivity or idleness, 16 students representing (4.4%) said UMYUK students were mostly abusing drugs as a result of their poor academic performance, 11 students representing (3.0%) said societal failure was the factor that mostly leads to students drug abuse. Lastly, 14 students representing (3.8%) of the students said students mostly abused drugs as a result of health challenges.

This indicated that, Peer-group was the most common factor leading students to drug abuse in UMYUK.

Table 12 Measures to Curb Drug Abuse among Students in UMYUK

Measures	Frequency	Percentage
Creating NDLEA Office within the Campuses.	116	31.7
Periodic Presentation on Effect of Drug Abuse.	83	22.7
Proper Upbringing.	35	9.6
Consultation of Medical Professionals when Sick.	15	4.1
Introducing Strict Rules on Drug Abuse.	77	21.0
Introducing related Courses to Effects of Drug Abuse.	40	10.9
Total	366	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2023

In table 12 some important measures to curb drug abuse among students in UMYUK were suggested where majority 116 of respondents the representing (31.7%) said creating NDLEA office within the campuses can help to reduce drug abuse among students. Secondly, 83 of them representing (22.7%) of the respondents suggested that periodic presentation on effect of drug abuse was among the measures to be taking in curbing drug abuse among students, 35 students representing (9.6%) said proper upbringing can help, 15 of them representing (4.1%) said consultation of medical professionals when sick can help in reducing drug abuse among students.

Moreover, a large number of the respondents 77 representing (21%) advised that introducing strict rules on drug abuse can help in reducing the rate of drug abuse among students while 40 respondents representing (10.9%) introducing course related to effect of drug abuse can help to reduce drug abuse among UMYUK students.

This indicated that, the most effective measure to curb drug abuse among the student of UMYUK was to establish NDLEA Office within the UMYUK Campus with (31.7), and then followed by Periodic Presentation on the Effects of Drug Abuse on the Academic Performance of Students with representing (22.7%), and then Introducing a course related to Effects of Drug Abuse with (10.9).

Table 13 Students academic performance while abusing drugs in UMYUK

Students' Academic Performance while Abusing Drugs in UMYUK	Frequency	Percentage
Good	51	13.9
Very Good	17	4.6
Poor	107	29.2
Very Poor	76	20.8
Not Engaged	115	31.4
Total	366	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2023

Table 13 shows the responses on students' performance while abusing drugs. 51 respondents representing (13.9%) said their performance was good, 17 respondents representing (4.6%) said their performance was very good, 107 respondents representing 29.2% said their performance was poor, 76 of them representing (20.8%) said their performance is very poor while 115 (31.4%) were among those that do not engaged in drug abuse.

This shows that students' performance was poor when engaged in drug abuse.

Hypothesis testing:

H_0 There is no significant relationship between drug abuse and academic performance of students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Table 14: Chi-square result for hypothesis 2

N	χ^2_{cal}	Df	α	<i>P – value</i>	Decision
366	52.992	24	0.05	0.034	Significant

Source: SPSS Output, 2023

Table 14 is a chi square result test of the relationship between drugs abused and the academic performance of students in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina. The result shows that the chi-square p-value was 0.034 at 24 degree of freedom which is less than the significant value 0.05 (**Pvalue < 0.05**). As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significant. That is, there is significant relationship between drugs abused and the academic performance of students in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina.

Findings

The study revealed that students' performance was affected when engaged in drug abuse. This indicated that drug abuse has a detrimental effect on the academic performance of students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina. In line with this finding, a similar study was also reported that, Abuse of drugs by students has been linked to poor academic performance. A study by Njeru and Ngesu (2014) indicated that 52% of students believed that drug abuse causes poor performance as 30% agreed that their colleagues who abused drugs develop aggressive behavior. The findings of different other studies have shown that declining grades, absenteeism from class/other activities, and increased potential for dropping out of school or university are problems associated with adolescent alcohol and drug abuse (Didenko&Pankratz, 2007). Additionally, low level of commitment to education and higher absence rates appear to be related to alcohol and drug use among adolescents in the universities and colleges (Hassan, 2020).

The study found that Codeine was most commonly abused drug among the students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina. This could be an indication that Codeine is common everywhere and accessible to students. Contrary research conducted in Tanzania's Public Schools revealed that, the use of drugs such astobacco (cigarette) and alcohol are more consumed by students simply because they are culturally, socially and legally acceptable in Tanzania and these drugs are locally produced Paulo, P. M. (2017).

The study foundstudents' drop-out from School was the major effect of drug abuse among the students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina as indicated from the table 8 which representing (23.2) of the total population as stated by the respondents during the research, this shows that, many students were withdrawn from the university as a result of drug abuse.Study similar to this finding also revealed that, issues of declining grades, absenteeism from school and other academic activities, and increased potential for dropping out of school are problems associated with students' drug abuse and also lead to low level of commitment to education and higher truancy rates appear to be related to drug use among the students of higher institutions of learning. (Abubakar et al., 2022).

The study also revealed that, Peer Group was the most dangerous and major cause of drug abuse among the students of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina as indicated from the table10 that (55.5%) of

the drug abusers were forced into the behavior as a result of socialization with bad friends during their staying in the University Campus. In line with this finding, another research was also conducted in Malaysia by Dr. Tam under Jeffery Cheah School of Medicine and Health Sciences, Monash University (2015) stated that, Peer group, curiosity and stress are contributing factors to drug abuse, peer group also pressure due to characterized by the desire to be accepted among the friends or social circles, the desire to achieve success in a competitive world and warped (materialistic) values system in the society such as the craze to get rich quick. as cited in (Rohana Y. and Amina L. M, 2015). In another study by Ghasem and Azita (2014) it was reported that 46.7% of drug abuse in Isfahan City India by adolescents, was as a result of peer influence. A study among students in Benin City Nigeria reported that 84.7% of respondents strongly agreed that peer pressure influences the use and abuse of drugs (Adeyemo et al., 2016).

CONCLUSION

Based on the data collected, presented, and analyzed, and literature consulted, this study concludes that without a doubt, drug abuse is a serious negative attitude among students of tertiary institutions in Nigeria, especially Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina, as the focus of this study, where it has been seen that poor academic performance is just one of so many negative effects of drug abuse among students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The Department of Guidance and Counseling in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University should be reinforced in counseling students on the negative effects of Peer-group influence which has a detrimental effect on their academic performance. The Management of Musa Yar'adua University should introduce courses related to effects of drug abuse and its related consequences to students, even if it is one a (1) credit unit, and make it compulsory to all students. Further, the Management of the university should liaise with NDLEA office Katsina during the admission exercise so as to help the university in identify those who are drug abusers and give them brief rehabilitation training before admitting them. Finally, parents should put more effort on proper upbringing of their children so as to make the society free from any social problems, because lack of proper upbringing is the major factor that lead to negative peer group influence.

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